

Our Heritage, Our Stories and Kinloch Historical Society: Digital Community Archive Development on the Isle of Lewis

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The OHOS team and Kinloch volunteers share a joke in-between sharing ideas about their archive.

On October 28-29, a team from the [University of Glasgow Information Studies Department](#), [The National Archives](#), and the [Manchester University History Department](#) visited [Kinloch Historical Society](#), to work with the staff and volunteers to co-create a digital workflow that would allow them to explore the potential of digitising the Kinloch archives.

The gorgeous view from the Kinloch Historical Society Community Hub.

Thousands of small, independent, heritage organisations across the UK take different approaches to creating and sharing their content digitally. This material is digitised in a variety of ways, and long-term preservation of the material can be challenging. A key part of the OHOS project is developing a series of case studies about community heritage organisations with ambitions to digitise their collections and make them accessible online.

Here are some examples of some of the materials created by Kinloch Historical Society that have been generated for and by the community.

Kinloch Historical Society was selected as a case study by the OHOS project, which will follow and document the archive's digitisation plans in the coming months to highlight any questions or challenges they may face. This will be used to inform documentation the project will develop about managing and sustaining digital archives that will be widely applicable to small, independent local archives. Since participating in developing the case study will require a time commitment by staff and volunteers at Kinloch, OHOS was able to offer a small grant to offset this and allow the Historical Society to develop their digitisation plans with the University team.

During the two days, the team – Professor Lorna M. Hughes, Professor Ann Gow, Nella McNicol from the University of Glasgow, Professor Hannah Barker from the University of Manchester, and Dr Ashleigh Hawkins from TNA (who took part remotely via Zoom) worked with Chairman of the Society Ken Roddy Mackay, Heritage Manager Anna McKenzie, and several volunteers. The workshops sought to establish consistent basic metadata and archival description practices bespoke to Kinloch that could facilitate the inclusion of local, expert knowledge and the Gaelic language.

The work carried out during the visit also included scoping the archival collections, including selecting key collections for digitisation. The collections in the archive at Kinloch include materials such as the records of the old Balallan school; photos; papers; moving image and audio materials. It also holds contemporary records, including materials related to the development of windfarms on the Island. It was apparent to the team visiting that these collections would be of huge value to historians, educators, and the public.

By creating digital collections, this would enable Kinloch and other community archives that hold similarly rich materials to build digital bridges between their audiences and their collections. The potential is boundless: from linking their collections with scattered families around the world, to linking back to the communities that matter to them: encouraging local youth to engage with their heritage through education and sharing intergenerational knowledge, while simultaneously providing an opportunity to bring funding, income, and tourists from diasporic communities to their home. Community-generated digital content held by local archives provide enhanced access to source materials that complement, contradict, and correct official histories and narratives.

Examples of the different types of archive materials Kinloch Historical Society holds. Photos. 1/3

Examples of the different types of archive materials Kinloch Historical Society holds. Film reel. 2/3

Examples of the different types of archive materials Kinloch Historical Society holds. Various local artefacts. 3/3

A key aspect of the visit was to set up a digital workflow for Kinloch, including testing a news scanning workstation purchased for the project and reviewing options for cataloguing and managing digital images created. The workflow is intended to be modular and adaptable, so that volunteers can help with digitisation and cataloguing. We hope that in the coming years, students from the University of Glasgow can carry out work placement at Kinloch some of the other comainn eachdraidh (local historical societies) across the Outer Hebrides.

The visit also included a meeting of Comann Dualchas Innse Gall/Outer Hebrides Heritage Forum, and an opportunity for an open discussion about what is needed to support and sustain digital heritage. Representatives from a number of the Comunn Eachdraidh attended, including Isle of Scalpay, Grimsay Community Association, Ness Historical Society, The Islands Book Trust, Stornoway Historical Society, Paice Historical Society, Hebridean Connections, the Angus Macleod Archive, Hebrides People, and Kildonan Museum. These groups provided invaluable information about the unique challenges they face when collecting, storing and preserving their community-generated digital content.

A snap from the Heritage Forum Group meeting

Throughout the visit, it was important for the University group to learn from staff and volunteers at Kinloch and other members of the heritage forum about their ambitions for digital development, what is needed, what works and what doesn't, in order to help shape documentation and policy recommendations for community-generated digital collections. Many organisations have had short term, project funding, and face challenges in developing sustainable digital programmes. The final OHOS project outputs will include policy documents for the National Heritage Lottery Fund and other funders, so it is vital that community heritage groups shape these recommendations.

This was not the first visit to Kinloch Historical Society by Professor Hughes: she visited in 2021 to discuss ideas for digitisation with Kinloch and other archives across the Outer Hebrides as part of a research project funded by the Royal Society of Edinburgh. As a descendant of the MacLeods at 18 Balallan she is very familiar with the area and its heritage.

This is a photograph of Professor Hughes' father, James, who grew up at 18 Ballallan. The OHOS team used this photograph during the workshop to demonstrate the scanning equipment.

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